

determined by half integral method. As the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of all the metal complexes, except the La^{3+} and Nd^{3+} complexes, was found to be less than 1.78 log unit, they were computed by least square method. The results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEP-WISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

	$t = 25^\circ$						
	$\mu = 0.1 M$						
	Cations						
	H^+	La^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Y^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}
$\log K_1$	8.40	8.20	7.85	7.13	7.10	6.09	5.48
$\log K_2$	3.20	5.47	5.00	4.99	5.47	4.97	4.55

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Viscosity Equation of Strong Electrolyte Solutions Involving Cube Root and First Power of Concentration and "Effective Ionic Diameter"

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It has been shown in earlier publications¹⁻³ that the expression for κ (kappa) in the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes has to be modified and the modified kappa denoted by κ_m should be expressed as $(2e^3/DkTa)^{1/3}(2n)^{1/3}$ for 1:1 electrolytes, where 'a' represents the minimum distance of approach of two oppositely charged ions and has been termed as the 'effective ionic diameter', n the number of ions per cc of a particular species and the other terms have their usual significance.

Jones *et al*⁴⁻⁶ have shown that the variation of viscosity of strong electrolyte solutions upto about

0.1 N or 0.2 N can be represented accurately by the following equations:

$$\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_r represents the relative viscosity, C the concentration and A and B are constants.

It follows from the work of Falkenhagen *et al*⁷⁻⁸ that $A\sqrt{C}$ in equation (1) can be replaced by $(S/\beta)\beta\sqrt{C}$, where $\beta\sqrt{C}$ stands for κ (kappa) and S and β are constants which can be calculated from theory. At 25° for a 1:1 electrolyte $\beta=0.329 \times 10^8$.

In the expression $(S/\beta)\beta\sqrt{C}$ or $(S/\beta)\kappa$ deduced by Falkenhagen *et al*, κ_m may be substituted in place of κ and the expression $(S/\beta)\kappa_m$ may be used instead of $A\sqrt{C}$ in equation (1). Thus modified, equation (1) may be written as:

$$\eta_r = 1 + (S/\beta)\kappa_m + BC \quad \dots (2)$$

Putting $n = NC/1000$, substituting the numerical values of the universal constants and expressing 'a' in Angström unit in κ_m , and since $\kappa_m = (1.22/\sqrt{a})(\beta)[(C)^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}]$, equation (2) may be written as

$$\eta_r = 1 + S \left(\frac{1.22}{\sqrt{a}} \right) [C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}] + BC \quad \dots (2a)$$

In equation (2a), $C_0^{1/3}$ is a small constant; C_0 representing that concentration of the electrolyte at which the ion-atmosphere of the central ion and interionic attraction disappear. C_0 is very small but not zero.

At 25° the values of S recorded in Harned and Owen's book⁹ are 0.006 for NaCl and 0.005 for KCl and the values of $\sqrt{a}$ collected from the author's publications are 2.36 for NaCl and 2.34 for KCl. Therefore, for NaCl at 25°, equation (2a), after simplification and evaluation of the constants B and $(C_0)^{1/3}$ from the experimental data, may be expressed as

$$\eta_r = 1 + [0.0031(C)^{1/3} + 0.088(C) - 0.000106] \quad \dots (2b)$$

Similarly for KCl, equation (2a) in its simplified form is written as

$$\eta_r = 1 + [0.0026(C)^{1/3} - 0.0081(C) - 0.000109] \quad \dots (2c)$$

In Table 1 are recorded the values of η_r observed and calculated [denoted as $(\eta_r)_{obs.}$ and $(\eta_r)_{cal.}$] of the aforesaid electrolytes collected from the papers of Jones *et al*⁴⁻⁶. In column 1 of the table are mentioned the electrolyte and the equation used.

It will be noticed that the agreement between the observed and calculated values of η_r is satisfactory. Satisfactory results have also been obtained with KBr, KI and NH_4Cl investigated so far. It may be pointed out that equation (2a) indicates a

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF η_r OF SOLUTIONS OF NaCl AND KCl WITH C AT 25°

		C					
		0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
NaCl	$(\eta_r)_{obs.}$	1.00043	1.00081	1.00146	1.00259	1.00544	1.00995
	$(\eta_r)_{cal.}$	{ 1.00046	1.00086	1.00144	1.00250	1.00544	1.01013
KCl	$(\eta_r)_{obs.}$	{ 1.00019	1.00030	1.00040	1.00044	1.00045	1.00025
	$(\eta_r)_{cal.}$	{ 1.00020	1.00030	1.00037	1.00045	1.00044	1.00029

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method of determining 'a' from viscosity measurements, since, 'S' can be calculated from theory. Furthermore, at $C=C_0$, $(C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3})=0$ and hence $B = (\eta_r - 1)/C_0$ and as inter-ionic attraction disappears at C_0 , B should be an additive property of the ions as observed by Cox and Wolfenden¹⁰.

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Synthesis and Cardiovascular Activity of Substituted-4-Azetidinones†

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THE cyclo addition of chloroacetyl chloride and thioglycolic acid in different anils on azomethine group, $-CH=N-$, such as thenylidene¹, *p*-(2'-thianlylidene amino) acetophenone¹ yields azetidines and thiazolidinones.

The azetidines of 2-acetylphenothiazine have not been synthesized so far. Moreover, the phenothiazine nucleus possesses potent biological activities²⁻⁵ including cardiovascular activity⁶. 2-Acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (III) was condensed with substituted aromatic aldehydes to yield arylidene-2-acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (IVa-1) by refluxing in dry toluene in the presence of glacial acetic acid⁷.

The cycloaddition reaction of monochloroacetyl chloride on azomethine group ($-CH=N-$) in (IVa-1) yielded the corresponding substituted-4-azetidines (Va-1). Compounds thus synthesized are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer, Model 137 spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}). NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 90D instrument using TMS as internal standard. TLC was done on silica gel G.

2-Acetyl phenothiazine (I) and 2-acetyl-10-(chloroacetyl) phenothiazine (II) were prepared by known methods.

2-Acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (III) : A mixture of 2-acetyl-10-(chloroacetyl) phenothiazine (0.03 mole) in absolute ethanol and hydrazine hydrate (99%) (0.45 mole) was refluxed for 20 hr, solvent was removed and the solid mass that separated out was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 215-216°, yield 80%. (Found: N, 13.01. $C_{16}H_{18}N_3O_2S$ requires N, 13.42%). IR of III showed characteristic bands at 3420 ($-NH$) and 1690 ($-C=O$) cm^{-1} .

Arylidene-2-acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazines (IVa-1) : To a solution of 2-acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (III) (0.01 mole) in toluene (dry, 50 ml) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid was added the respective substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mole) and the mixture refluxed for 10 to 12 hr.

Scheme

† Part of the work will be incorporated in the Ph.D. thesis of A.K.

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